

		Standard Operating Procedure REMEDi4ALL-SOPs
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Version:	01	
Valid from:	15/08/24	

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2 Goal and Area of Application

Phospholipidosis is a storage disorder of excessive accumulation of phospholipids in lysosomes that can be drug-induced. Understanding the role of drug-induced phospholipidosis (DIPL) in ongoing drug screenings is necessary to better distinguish between on-target and side effects as well as for putative endosomal pathway disturbance.

3 Definitions and Abbreviations

SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SP	Screening Port
ITMP	Institut für Translationale Medizin und Pharmakologie
RT	Room Temperature (20-25 °C)
i.a.	In Assay
DIPL	Drug Induced Phospholipidosis
DMEM	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium
HCS	High Content Screening
PBS	Phosphate-Buffered Saline
FCS	Fetal Calf Serum
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
ms	milliseconds

4 Method

4.1 General

This SOP describes the procedure of measuring Drug-Induced-Phospholipidosis staining in VeroE6 cell line in combination with an Operetta HCS system (Revvity) at Fraunhofer ITMP-SP. HCS LipidTOX™ Red Phospholipidosis Detection Reagent (Invitrogen™, #H34351) is a fluorescent dye that is used to stain the cells and to detect induction of phospholipidosis. The dye does not influence cell growth and is well-retained after aldehyde fixation.

4.2 Information for consumables / chemicals / equipment

Product Name	Supplier	Catalog Number
HCS LipidTOX™ Red Phospholipidosis Detection Reagent (1000X), for cellular imaging	Invitrogen TM	H34351
CellMask™ plasma membrane stain	Invitrogen TM	C10046
Hoechst 33258	Sigma Aldrich Inc., MO, USA	94403
e.g. Formaldehyde solution (PFA)	Sigma Aldrich Inc., MO, USA	252549
Amiodarone	Sigma Aldrich Inc., MO, USA	V0627

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DMEM; high glucose, no L-glutamine, no phenol red	Life Technologies GmbH	31053044
Vero E6	ATCC, USA	CRL-1586
e.g. PBS w/o Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺	Gibco, Life Technologies GmbH	14190250
e.g. Trypsin 0.05 % / EDTA 0.02% in PBS w/o Ca ²⁺	Capricorn	TRY-1B
e.g. FCS	Capricorn	10-FBS-11F
e.g. Penicillin 10,000 U/mL / Streptomycin 10,000 µg/mL	Gibco, Life Technologies GmbH	15140122
e.g. Glutamine	Gibco, Life Technologies GmbH	25030081
PhenoPlate 384-well, black, optically clear flat-bottom, tissue-culture treated	Revvity	6057302
DMSO	Carl Roth, Germany	HN47.1
Echo	Labcyte Inc., CA, USA	
Operetta CLS High-Content Analysis System	Revvity	HH16000020

4.3 Procedure

1. Compound addition

Compounds (10 µM i.a. concentration) and controls (amiodarone 10 µM i.a. concentration; DMSO 0.1 v/v %) are added using the Echo Liquid Handler (Labcyte). Due to requests of the Echo system, attention should be paid to the selected plate types to avoid the plate and transducer crash.

Important: PhenoPlate = CellCarrier plate in the Echo software

2. Cell seeding

VeroE6 cell line is used for detection of DIPL. Cells are culture in complete medium: DMEM (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium) supplemented with 10% FBS, 6 mM L-glutamine, 1% penicillin/streptomycin. Cells were harvested from a T175 cm² flask at 80% confluence by washing them once using 10 mL RT PBS and afterwards incubating the cells with 5 mL Trypsin 0.05% / EDTA 0.02% for 5 min. Cells are suspended using 10 mL of prewarmed cell culture media. VeroE6 cells are diluted to a concentration of 500,000 cells per mL in cell culture media supplemented with 1:1000 diluted HCS LipidTOX™ Red Phospholipidosis Detection Reagent (1000X). 20 µL of this suspension is added to each well of a 384 well PhenoPlate. Cells are incubated for 24 h at 37 °C and 5 % CO₂.

3. Detection

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Cells are fixed by addition of 20 μL /well 8 % formaldehyde solution. After 30 min incubation time at RT fixation buffer is removed and cells are washed with 50 μL /well PBS. Cells are stained for 45 min with 20 μL /well of CellMask™ plasma membrane stain (1:3,000) and Hoechst 33258 (1:10,000) diluted in PBS. Staining solution was removed and cells were washed 3 times with 50 μL /well PBS.

Important: Increased fixation-time may result in loss of signal (DIPL spots) and enhanced background.

Induction of DIPL was detected at 0 μm height of detection with 5 images/well on the Operetta CLS High-Content Analysis System using following parameters.

Channel-name	Power	Exposure time
Alexa 594	60 %	20 ms
Hoechst 33258	100 %	20 ms
CellMask Deep red	100 %	80 ms

Fig. 1. Example of a positive control (left, amiodarone 20 μM) and negative control (right, DMSO 0.1 v/v %) effect. Nuclei stain using Hoechst 33258, cytoplasm stain using CellMask Deep Red.

4. Analysis

Image analysis is performed using Columbus image analysis software. The analysis includes 5 steps:

- Nuclei identification (Fig.1-A)
- Removal of border objects (nuclei are completely displayed) = “selected population” (Fig.1-B)
- Cytoplasm identification in the selected population (Fig.1-C)
- Calculation of DIPL signal in the cytoplasm (intensity) (Fig.1-D)
- Identification of spots (Fig.1-E)
- Definition of results that should be calculated (Fig.1-F)

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analysis_spots_selectedmean05

Input Image

Find Nuclei

Channel: HOECHST 3325

ROI Population: None

ROI Region:

Method: B

Output Population: Nuclei

Comment:

Select Population

Find Cytoplasm

Calculate Intensity Properties

Find Spots

Define Results

Sequence Comment

Nuclei

Population: Nuclei

A

analysis_spots_selectedmean05

Input Image

Find Nuclei

Select Population

Population: Nuclei

Method: Common Filter

Remove Border Objects:

Output Population: Nuclei Selected

Comment:

Find Cytoplasm

Calculate Intensity Properties

Find Spots

Define Results

Sequence Comment

Nuclei Nuclei Selected

Population: Nuclei

B

Population: Nuclei Selected

C

Population: Nuclei Selected

D

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analysis_spots_selectedmean05

Input Image

Find Nuclei

Select Population

Find Cytoplasm

Calculate Intensity Properties

Find Spots + - >

Channel: Alexa 594

ROI Population: Nuclei Selected

ROI Region: Cytoplasm

Method: B

Output Population: Spots

Comment

Define Results

Sequence Comment

Spots Nuclei Selected

Population: Spots

E

Find Spots

Define Results >

Method: List of Outpu

Population: Nuclei

Population: Nuclei Selected

Number of Objects:

Apply to All: Individual S

Intensity Cytoplasm: Alexa 594 Mean

Total Spot Area: Mean

Relative Spot Intensity: Mean

Number of Spots: Mean

Number of Spots per Area of Cytoplasm:

Population: Spots

Method:

Object Results

Nuclei Nuclei Selected Spots

Population: Nuclei

F

Figure 1. Workflow of DIPL data analysis in Columbus Image Analysis Software. Nuclei identification (A) Removal of border objects (nuclei are completely displayed) = "selected"

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population” (B) Cytoplasm identification in the selected population (C) Calculation of DIPL signal in the cytoplasm (intensity) (D) Identification of spots (E) Definition of results that should be calculated (F)

5 Further applicable resources

Manufacturer manual for HCS LipidTOX™ Red Phospholipidosis Detection Reagent (1000X), for cellular imaging:

- <https://assets.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets%2FMSG%2Fmanuals%2Fmp34350.pdf>

6 Document history

Guidance: Record the version history and reasons for updates.

SOP version	Reason
Version 1	Initial draft of document
<i>Version 2</i>	<i>E.g., update of section 7</i>
<i>Version 3</i>	<i>E.g., correction of typos</i>

7 Annex

No annex

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